

Supplement E1

Figure E1. A) Case 1, lesion in septal region (TV: 9.9 cm³ PTV: 97.3 cm³), **B)** Case 2, lesion in midventricular and apical anteroseptal segments (TV: 13.9 cm³ PTV: 62.2 cm³), **C)** Case 3, lesion in myocardial substrate (TV: 14.2 cm³ PTV: 82.7 cm³). PTV is shown in red, TV is shown in purple, stomach is shown in yellow and coronaries are shown in blue and green.

Table E1. Technical information about submitted plans per participating centre. 22/23/22 plans were submitted for case 1/2/3, respectively. Abbreviations: ASC: Aperture Shape Controller, CM: convergence mode, Dp: Dose prescription, MI: Modulation Index (defined as: Total MU/25), N.A.: not available, TPS: treatment planning system.

Centre	TPS	Version	Algorithm	Grid Size [mm]	Case 01			Case 02			Case 03		
					Prescription Method/Isodose	Estimated Treatment Time [min]	Additional Information	Prescription Method/Isodose	Estimated Treatment Time [min]	Additional Information	Prescription Method/Isodose	Estimated Treatment Time [min]	Additional Information
1	Raystation	9A	CCC	N.A.	V100%>=95%	2.92	5581 MU MI=2.23	V100%>=95%	3.22	6359 MU MI=2.54	V100%>=95%	3.6	7042 MU MI=2.82
2	Eclipse	15.6.8	AcurosXB	2.5	V25=100%	10.0	ASC: moderate	V100%=25Gy	10.0	ASC: moderate	V100%=25Gy	10.0	ASC: moderate
2	Precision	2.0.1.1	Monte Carlo	like CT scan	25 Gy to 75% isodose	71	collimator- sizes: 15-50 mm	25 Gy to 75% isodose	74	collimator- sizes: 15-50 mm	25 Gy to 75% isodose	75	collimator- sizes: 10-35 mm
3	Precision	2.0.1.1	Monte Carlo	0.94 x 2 x 0.94 / 1.46 x 1.50 x 1.46 / 1.56 x 2 x 1.56	25 Gy to 85% isodose	31	# beams: 23 / # segments: 27	25 Gy to 80% isodose	44	# beams: 37 / # segments: 52	25 Gy to 80% isodose	46	# beams: 35 / # segments: 48
4	Eclipse	15.6	AcurosXB	1.25	N.A.	N.A.	ASC: off, 7553.8 MU, MI=3.02	N.A.	N.A.	ASC: off 8903.3 MU, MI=3.56	N.A.	N.A.	ASC: off 8845 MU, MI=3.54
5	Eclipse	16.1	AAA	N.A.	N.A.	5.33	7660 MU, MI=3.02	N.A.	5.48	8840 MU, MI=3.54	N.A.	7.62	7262 MU, MI=2.9
6	Eclipse	16.1	AcurosXB	1.5	Mean TV dose =30Gy, V25Gy=96.4%, PTV edited	8.7	ASC: low, 10209.3 MU, MI=4.08	Mean TV dose =30Gy, V25Gy=96.2%	12.2	ASC: low, 18837.6 MU, MI=7.54	Mean TV dose =30Gy, V25Gy=97.2%	12.9	ASC: low, 15114.4 MU, MI= 6.05
7	Pinnacle	16.0.2	Adaptative Convolve	2	D98%=25Gy	4.5	N.A.	D98%=25Gy	5.1	N.A.	D98%=25Gy	4.6	N.A.
8	Multiplan	5.2.1	Monte Carlo	like CT scan	20 Gy to 76% isodose	54	collimator- sizes: 7.5-60 mm	22 Gy to 74% isodose	66	collimator- sizes: 7.5-40 mm	22 Gy to 72% isodose	69	collimator- sizes: 7.5-50 mm
9	Raystation	10A	CCC	2	V25Gy=95%	6.22	9286 MU, MI=3.71	V25Gy=95%	6.72	9980 MU, MI=3.99	V25Gy=95%	6.78	10145 MU, MI=4.06
10	Eclipse	16.1	AcurosXB	1.25	N.A.	6.68	ASC: off 9352 MU, MI=3.74	N.A.	6.26	ASC: off 8074 MU, MI=3.23	N.A.	5.52	ASC: off 6950 MU, MI=2.78

11	Raystation	8B, 8.1.2.5	Monte Carlo	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
12	Eclipse	16.1.0	AcurosXB	1	25 Gy covers >95% PTV volume	6.0	4 half arcs, 120-300°	25 Gy covers >95% PTV volume	6.0	4 half arcs, 179-300°	25 Gy covers 90% PTV volume	6.0	4 half arcs, 179-300°
12	Viewray	5.4.0.97	Monte Carlo	2	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	25 Gy covers >95% PTV volume	18	14 beams, 312-213°	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.
13	Monaco	5.51	Monte Carlo	2	D93%=25Gy	6.2	6049 MU, MI=2.42	D95%=25Gy	7.35	8083 MU, MI=3.23	D95%=25Gy	6.93	7627 MU, MI=3.05
14	Eclipse	13.7	AAA	1.25	edited PTV, V25Gy=90%	4.81	max field 9.3 x 10 cm	V25Gy= 99.85%	5.47	max field 8,5 x 7,8 cm	V25Gy= 95%	5.61	max field 10,2 x 9,1 cm
15	RayStation	11A	CCC	1	25 Gy to 81% idosose	85	collimator sizes: 15, 20, 25, 30 mm	25 Gy to 87% idosose	90	MLC used	25 Gy to 77% idosose	78	MLC used
16	Monaco	5.11	Monte Carlo	3 (resampled to 1)	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	5.75	5905 MU, MI=2.36	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	7.0	7752 MU, MI=3.1	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	7.67	8786 MU, MI=3.51
16	Monaco	5.51	Monte Carlo	3 (resampled to 1)	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	22.7	8398 MU, MI=3.36	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	30.7	11846 MU, MI=4.74	V25Gy>95%, max dose 35Gy	25.8	9654 MU, MI=3.86
17	Eclipse	16.01.03	AcurosXB	1.25	V25Gy=99%	6.41	ASC + CM: off, max. MU objective: 7000, 7244.7 MU, MI=2.9	V25Gy=99.85%	8.23	ASC + CM: off, max. MU objective: 9000, 9595.7 MU, MI=3.84	V25Gy=68.5%	6.46	ASC + CM: off, max. MU objective: 7000, 7044.1 MU, MI=2.82
18	Precision	3.1	Ray-Trace	0.94 x 2 x 0.94 / 1.46 x 1.50 x 1.46 / 1.56 x 2 x 1.56	V25Gy=90.2%, 80% isodose	72	collimator sizes: 20, 35 mm, 151 beams	V25Gy=95%, 76.5% isodose	74	collimator sizes: 15, 25 mm, 154 beams	V25Gy=90.1%, 77% isodose	102	collimator sizes: 10, 20, 35 mm, 245 beams
19	Eclipse	16.1	AAA	1.25	V95%Dp>= 95%PTV	N.A.	N.A.	V95%Dp>= 95%PTV	N.A.	N.A.	V95%Dp>= 95%PTV	N.A.	N.A.
20	Raystation	10b	CCC 5.4	2	V100%>=97%	2.65	5582 MU, Mi=2.23	V100%>=97%	2.63	5540 MU, MI=2.22	V100%>=97%	2.4	5014 MU, MI=2.01

Table E2. Crowd technical and planning strategy data for the submitted plans. 22/23/22 plans were submitted for case 1/2/3, respectively. Underdosing was defined as $D_{0.035ccm} \leq 20$ Gy for A_LAD + A_LCX and $D_{0.035ccm} \leq 19$ Gy for stomach due to values out of treatment plan. For case 03 the compromise is defined as coronary arteries doses ≤ 25 Gy, but ≥ 20 Gy. Abbreviations: A_LAD: left anterior descending coronary artery, A_LCX: left circumflex coronary artery, HU: Hounsfield Unit, Linac: linear accelerator, MRI: magnetic resonance imaging, conv.: conventional, N.A.: not available, OAR: organs at risk.

	Treatment technique	Beam energy	OAR overlap management	Artifact management
Case 01	MRI Linac: 1 (4.5%) Particles (protons): 1 (4.5%) robotic Linac: 5 (23%) conv. Linac: 15 (68 %)	6FFF: 16 (73%) 7FFF: 1 (4.5%) 10FFF: 4 (18%) 70-140 MeV: 1 (4.5%)	PTV coverage (no OAR sparing): 4 (18%) Underdosing for A_LAD: 7 (32%) Underdosing for stomach: 7 (32%) Underdosing for both OARs: 4 (18%)	HU/density override: 8 (36%) Not necessary after recalculation: 3 (14%) None: 5 (23%) N.A.: 6 (27%)
Case 02	MRI Linac: 2 (9%) Particle (protons): 1 (4%) robotic Linac: 5 (22%) conv. Linac: 15 (65%)	6FFF: 17 (74%) 7FFF: 1 (4.5%) 10FFF: 4 (17%) 70-140 MeV: 1 (4.5%)	PTV coverage: 10 (43%) Underdosing for A_LAD: 13 (57%)	HU/density override (unspecified): 5 (22%) HU/density override (air): 2 (9%) density override (water): 10 (43%) None: 3 (13.0%) N.A.: 3 (13.0%)
Case 03	MRI Linac: 1 (4.5%) Particle (protons): 1 (4.5%) robotic Linac: 5 (23%) conv. Linac: 15 (68%)	6FFF: 16 (73%) 7FFF: 1 (4.5%) 10FFF: 4 (18%) 80-160 MeV: 1 (4.5%)	PTV coverage: 11 (50%) Compromise between A_LAD+A_LCX and PTV coverage due to patient situation: 4 (18%) Compromise between A_LCX and PTV coverage due to patient situation: 1 (4.5%) Underdosing for A_LAD+A_LCX: 5 (23%) Underdosing for A_LCX: 1 (4.5%)	No artifacts in or near treatment area.

Supplement E2: Details of the final vote on the treatment planning statements for STAR. Abbreviations: SBRT = Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy, STAR = Stereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation, GTV = Gross Tumor Volume, TV = (Clinical) Target Volume, ITV = Internal Target Volume, PTV = Planning Target Volume, OAR = Organs at Risk, ICD = Implantable Cardioverter Defibrillators, ICRU = International Commission on Radiation Units and Measurements

Guideline	Score frequency					agreement in %	strength of agreement	median	IQR
	5 strongly agree	4	3 neither agree nor disagree	2	1 strongly disagree				
<i>General requirements: For SBRT and STAR, international guidelines, best practice recommendations and reviews for technological and procedural requirements have been published to ensure safe, effective, and high-quality treatments [5, 6, 11].</i>									
For STAR treatment planning, technological quality requirements and best practice guidelines for SBRT and STAR must be considered. [5, 7, 8, 14, 15, 16]	16	4	0	0	0	100	strong agreement	5	0
For STAR treatment planning, respiratory and cardiac motion management strategies and their uncertainties must be considered based on best practice guidelines for SBRT and STAR [5, 6, 37] and the patient specific target and critical organs location and motion [36].	16	3	0	1	0	95	strong agreement	5	0
<i>Prescription dose, trade-offs, and documentation: For SBRT treatments with small photon beams, recommendations of the ICRU on prescribing, recording, and reporting [12] as well as dose limitations for several OAR in the whole body [21] have been published. For STAR, a GTV is not defined while the TV is defined as the substrate in the heart causing the arrhythmia [11]. The ITV covers the TV and its uncompensated respiratory and cardiac motion [6]. The PTV covers the ITV and includes a safety margin for treatment delivery uncertainties [5, 12].</i>									
The dose for STAR with small photon beams must be prescribed according to the ICRU report 91 [12] to the surrounding isodose that covers an optimal portion of the PTV while adhering to extra-cardiac OAR and cardiac substructure dose limitations.	9	7	4	0	0	80	strong agreement	4	1
For well-known single fraction dose limits of extra-cardiac OAR [42, 21, 22], the dose trade-off in the PTV for STAR must be in favor of OAR sparing to minimize risks of severe and fatal toxicities [43]	9	11	0	0	0	100	strong agreement	4	1
Since dose limits for cardiac substructures are not well established [23-26, 27, 28, 44, 45], the dose trade-off in the PTV for STAR should be based on the clinical situation of the patient	12	7	1	0	0	95	strong agreement	5	1
The dosimetric plan information for STAR must be documented and reported according to the ICRU report 91 [12] with at minimum the PTV prescription dose, PTV D _{98%} , D _{50%} and D _{2%} , Target Volume (TV) D _{50%} , and D _{near_max} , and the D _{50%} for all extra-cardiac OAR and intracardiac substructures as defined in [9]	10	7	3	0	0	85	strong agreement	4.5	1

Dose inhomogeneity: Currently, a single fraction prescription dose of 25 Gy to the PTV surrounding isodose is the most used dose for STAR in clinical practice [4]. However, a single fraction of 25 Gy dose may not lead to catheter ablation-like fibrosis in the heart [17-20, 38, 39]. Even higher single fraction doses over 30 Gy may be required for creating transmural fibrosis [17, 18], but this could depend on the individual patient (e.g., patient age, underlying heart diseases, comorbidities, etc) and the passed time after treatment. Nevertheless, there is currently no evidence for increased therapeutic effects with higher doses or with high dose inhomogeneity and clinical studies are ongoing [44, NCT05765175, NCT05594368, NCT05913375].

The prescription dose and the dose inhomogeneity in the PTV should be based on the clinical situation of the patient, the desired treatment effect, and the target location with its surrounding extra-cardiac and cardiac OARs [4, NCT05258422]	9	9	1	1	0	90	strong agreement	4	1
Doses over 30 Gy are not necessary for creating therapeutic effects (e.g., reduction in ventricular tachycardia episodes) for STAR [1-4, 13, 18]	4	9	7	0	0	65	no agreement	4	1
Doses over 30 Gy may be required for creating catheter ablation-like fibrosis for STAR and may potentially increase therapeutic effects [44, NCT05765175, NCT05594368, NCT05913375, NCT05258422]	1	7	10	2	0	40	no agreement	3	1
If higher doses over 30 Gy are considered for STAR, these doses should be confined to the target volume and not placed in the PTV margin zone (PTV minus ITV) or in PTV overlapping extra-cardiac OAR or cardiac substructures [7]	9	9	0	2	0	90	strong agreement	4	1

Dose limits for cardiac substructures: Dose limitations to extra cardiac OAR are well known for single fraction SBRT [22, 46], however dose limitations for cardiac substructures for STAR are not well known. As an example, currently no dose-volume relationship between the left ventricle dose and changes in left ventricle ejection fraction was found [25, 26]. Guidelines for specific dose limitations can be found in Table 3.

For dose limitations on the coronary arteries as defined in [9], the individual patient anatomy and coronary function, indication for STAR as well as the location of the target volume must be considered for STAR [25-28]	11	9	0	0	0	100	strong agreement	5	1
For dose limitations on the cardiac valves as defined in [9], the individual patient anatomy and the valves functionality, the indication for STAR as well as the location of the target volume must be considered for STAR	8	12	0	0	0	100	strong agreement	4	1
For all other cardiac substructures as defined in [9], the dose limits are unknown at this time and the dose statistics for those structures must be reported in agreement with the ICRU report 91 [12] for all STAR cases	14	5	1	0	0	95	strong agreement	5	1

Beam technique planning: For beam technique planning, several guidelines and best practice guidelines exist for SBRT and for STAR from multi-center benchmarks studies [7, 8]. This STOPSTORM planning benchmark adds to the already well-established literature, however special attention needs to be put on ICD and artifacts from e.g., Left Ventricular Assist Devices (LVAT).

Photon beam energies > 6 MV and protons / ions should be used with caution in patients with ICDs [11]	9	8	2	0	1	85	strong agreement	4	1
For STAR with photon beams, energies ≤ 10 MV must be used due to safety regulations for ICDs [29, 30]	6	10	2	1	1	80	strong agreement	4	1
For STAR with photon beams, energies ≤ 6 MV should generally be used to avoid malfunction of ICDs [31, 32]	8	5	3	3	1	65	no agreement	4	2
Beams hitting the main ICD electronics must be avoided, a maximum dose of 2 Gy must not be exceeded and the dose must be reported accordingly [10]	8	7	3	0	2	75	moderate agreement	4	1.25
To avoid changes in functionality of the ICD electrodes (e.g., from electrical or from tissue changes), the dose to the ICD electrodes should be reduced to below 15 Gy if the PTV coverage is not affected by this reduction [33]	5	7	7	1	0	60	no agreement	4	1.25
Beams passing through artificial high-density structures (e.g., left ventricular assist devices) should be avoided [10]	4	11	4	1	0	75	moderate agreement	4	1.25
For STAR with c-arm linear accelerator systems, non-coplanar beam directions are not required to generate high quality treatment plans [7]	6	10	2	2	0	80	strong agreement	4	1
For STAR with c-arm linear accelerator systems, volumetric intensity modulated techniques are preferred for beam technique planning [7, 15, 16]	9	9	2	0	0	90	strong agreement	4	1
For STAR with multi-leaf collimators, complex plans with high modulation factor should be avoided to reduce interplay effects [40]	3	7	10	0	0	50	no agreement	3.5	1
<i>Dose calculation: The dose of SBRT treatment plans must be calculated as accurately as possible, however, large density inhomogeneities and respiratory and cardiac motion may impact the dose calculation accuracy for STAR.</i>									
Density override in the treatment planning systems of artifacts in or near the PTV ideally after the use of metal artifact reduction (MAR) algorithms is required for accurate dose calculation [34, 35]	7	10	3	0	0	85	strong agreement	4	1
In areas with large density inhomogeneities, the use of a dose calculation algorithm that considers lateral electron transport to correct for density inhomogeneities is required [5]	12	8	0	0	0	100	strong agreement	5	1
The maximum grid size for dose calculation should be 1–2 mm according to the target lesion dimensions and the image resolution for target definition [5]	14	4	1	1	0	90	strong agreement	5	1

Due to the potential of significant dose reductions from uncompensated residual target motion [69], the cardio-respiratory motion management strategy must be reported in alignment with the ICRU report 91 [12]	10	9	1	0	0	95	strong agreement	4.5	1
<i>Treatment times / dose rate: Treatment times for SBRT can vary significantly based on used technology, motion management strategy and beam technique planning [8]. For SBRT of solid tumors, limited evidence exists that the treatment time has a significant impact on efficacy and toxicity. For STAR, non-tumorous cells are targeted and prolonged dose delivery times could reduce the modulatory effects of single fraction doses [41]. Furthermore, STAR patients could be in poor condition due to the underlying heart diseases.</i>									
Treatment delivery times for STAR should be kept as short as possible considering all technical options (e.g., VMAT and FFF modes and ITV motion management concepts if clinically and technically reasonable) due to radiation biology considerations [41] and possibly poor patient conditions [4]	8	11	0	0	1	95	strong agreement	4	1

References

- [1] van der Ree MH, Blanck O, Limpens J, et al. Cardiac radioablation-A systematic review. *Heart Rhythm*. 2020;17(8):1381-92.
- [2] Kovacs B, Mayinger M, Schindler M, et al. Stereotactic radioablation of ventricular arrhythmias in patients with structural heart disease - A systematic review. *Radiother Oncol*. 2021;162:132-9.
- [3] Miszczyk M, Jadczyk T, Golba K, et al. Clinical Evidence behind Stereotactic Radiotherapy for the Treatment of Ventricular Tachycardia (STAR) - A Comprehensive Review. *J Clin Med*. 2021;10(6).
- [4] Grehn M, Mandija S, Miszczyk M, et al. Stereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation (STAR): the Standardized Treatment and Outcome Platform for Stereotactic Therapy Of Re-entrant tachycardia by a Multidisciplinary consortium (STOPSTORM.eu) and review of current patterns of STAR practice in Europe. *Europace*. 2023;25(4):1284-1295.
- [5] Schmitt D, Blanck O, Gauer T, et al. Technological quality requirements for stereotactic radiotherapy: Expert review group consensus from the DGMP Working Group for Physics and Technology in Stereotactic Radiotherapy. *Strahlenther Onkol*. 2020;196(5):421-43.
- [6] Lydiard S, Blanck O, Hugo G, et al. A Review of Cardiac Radioablation (CR) for Arrhythmias: Procedures, Technology, and Future Opportunities. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2021;109(3):783-800.
- [7] Kluge A, Ehrbar S, Grehn M, et al. Treatment Planning for Cardiac Radioablation: Multicenter Multiplatform Benchmarking for the RAdiosurgery for VENTricular TACHycardia (RAVENTA) Trial. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2022;114(2):360-72.
- [8] Giglioli FR, Garibaldi C, Blanck O, et al. Dosimetric Multicenter Planning Comparison Studies for Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy: Methodology and Future Perspectives. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2020;106(2):403-412.
- [9] Balgobind B, Visser J, Grehn M, et al. Refining Critical Structure Contouring in STereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation (STAR): Benchmark Results and Consensus Guidelines from the STOPSTORM.eu Consortium. *Radiother Oncol* 2023;189:109949
- [10] Mehrhof F, Bergengruen P, Gerds-Li JH, et al. Cardiac radioablation of incessant ventricular tachycardia in patients with terminal heart failure under permanent left ventricular assist device therapy-description of two cases. *Strahlenther Onkol*. 2023;199(5):511-519.

- [11] Krug D, Blanck O, Andratschke N, et al. Recommendations regarding cardiac stereotactic body radiotherapy for treatment refractory ventricular tachycardia. *Heart Rhythm*. 2021;18(12):2137-2145
- [12] Seuntjens J, Lartigau EF, Cora S, et al. ICRU report 91. Prescribing, recording, and reporting of stereotactic treatments with small photon beams. *J ICRU* 2014;14:1–160.
- [13] Robinson CG, Samson PP, Moore KMS, et al. Phase I/II Trial of Electrophysiology-Guided Noninvasive Cardiac Radioablation for Ventricular Tachycardia. *Circulation*. 2019;139(3):313-21.
- [14] Villaggi E, Hernandez V, Fusella M, et al. Plan quality improvement by DVH sharing and planner's experience: Results of a SBRT multicentric planning study on prostate. *Phys Med*. 2019;62:73-82.
- [15] Moustakis C, Blanck O, Chan MKH, et al. Planning Benchmark Study for Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy of Liver Metastases: Results of the DEGRO/DGMP Working Group on Stereotactic Radiation Therapy and Radiosurgery. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2022;113(1):214-227.
- [16] Giglioli FR, Clemente S, Esposito M, et al. Frontiers in planning optimization for lung SBRT. *Phys Med*. 2017;44:163-170.
- [17] Blanck O, Bode F, Gebhard M, et al. Dose-escalation study for cardiac radio-surgery in a porcine model. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2014;89(3):590-98.
- [18] Kim JS, Choi SW, Park Y, et al. Impact of High-Dose Irradiation on Human iPSC-Derived Cardiomyocytes Using Multi-Electrode Arrays: Implications for the Antiarrhythmic Effects of Cardiac Radioablation. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;23(1):351.
- [19] Zhang DM, Navara R, Yin T, et al. Cardiac radiotherapy induces electrical conduction reprogramming in the absence of transmural fibrosis. *Nat Commun*. 2021;12:5558.
- [20] Blanck O, Boda-Heggemann J, Hohmann S, et al. [Cardiac stereotactic radiotherapy induces electrical conduction reprogramming]. *Strahlenther Onkol*. 2022.198(2):209-11.
- [21] Grimm J, LaCouture T, Croce R, et al. Dose tolerance limits and dose volume histogram evaluation for stereotactic body radiotherapy. *J Appl Clin Med Phys*. 2011;12(2):3368.
- [22] Diez P, Hanna GG, Aitken KL, et al. UK 2022 Consensus on Normal Tissue Dose-Volume Constraints for Oligometastatic, Primary Lung and Hepatocellular Carcinoma Stereotactic Ablative Radiotherapy. *Clin Oncol (R Coll Radiol)*. 2022;34(5):288-300.
- [23] McWilliam A, Khalifa J, Vasquez Osorio E, Banfill K, Abravan A, Faivre-Finn C, et al. Novel Methodology to Investigate the Effect of Radiation Dose to Heart Substructures on Overall Survival. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2020;108(4):1073-81.
- [24] van der Ree MH, de Bruin-Bon RHA, Balgobind BV, Hoeksema WF, Visser J, van Laarhoven HWM, et al. Dose-dependent cardiac effects of collateral cardiac irradiation: Echocardiographic strain analysis in patients treated for extracardiac malignancies. *Heart Rhythm*. 2023;20(1):149-51.
- [25] Knutson NC, Samson PP, Hugo GD, et al. Radiation Therapy Workflow and Dosimetric Analysis from a Phase 1/2 Trial of Noninvasive Cardiac Radioablation for Ventricular Tachycardia. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2019;104(5):1114-1123.
- [26] van der Ree MH, Luca A, Herrera Siklody C, et al. Effects of stereotactic arrhythmia radioablation on left ventricular ejection fraction and valve function over time. *Heart Rhythm*. 2023:S1547-5271(23)02252-X.
- [27] Grise MA, Massullo V, Jani S, et al. Five-year clinical follow-up after intracoronary radiation: results of a randomized clinical trial. *Circulation*. 2002;105(23):2737-40.
- [28] Atkins KM, Chaunzwa TL, Lamba N, Bitterman DS, Rawal B, Bredfeldt J, et al. Association of Left Anterior Descending Coronary Artery Radiation Dose With Major Adverse Cardiac Events and Mortality in Patients With Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer. *JAMA Oncol*. 2021;7(2):206-19.
- [29] Gauter-Fleckenstein B, Israel CW, Dorenkamp M, et al. DEGRO/DGK guideline for radiotherapy in patients with cardiac implantable electronic devices. *Strahlenther Onkol* 2015;191:393-404.

- [30] Miften M, Mihailidis D, Kry SF, et al. Management of radiotherapy patients with implanted cardiac pacemakers and defibrillators: A Report of the AAPM TG-203. *Med Phys.* 2019;46(12):e757-e788.
- [31] Gauter-Fleckenstein B, Nguyen J, Jahnke L, et al. Interaction between CIEDs and modern radiotherapy techniques: Flattening filter free-VMAT, dose-rate effects, scatter radiation, and neutron-generating energies. *Radiother Oncol.* 2020;152:196-202.
- [32] Gauter-Fleckenstein B, Tülümen E, Rudic B, et al. Local dose rate effects in implantable cardioverter-defibrillators with flattening filter free and flattened photon radiation. *Strahlenther Onkol.* 2022;198(6):566-572.
- [33] van der Ree MH, Hoeksema WF, Luca A, et al. Stereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation: a multicenter pre-post intervention safety evaluation of the Implantable Cardioverter-Defibrillator function. *Radiother Oncol.* 2023;189:109910.
- [34] Parenica HM, Mavroidis P, Jones W, et al. VMAT Optimization and Dose Calculation in the Presence of Metallic Hip Prostheses. *Technol Cancer Res Treat.* 2019;18:1533033819892255.
- [35] Pawałowski, B., Ryczkowski, A., Panek, R. et al. Accuracy of the doses computed by the Eclipse treatment planning system near and inside metal elements. *Sci Rep* 12, 5974 (2022).
- [36] Stevens RRF, Hazelaar C, Fast MF, et al. STereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation (STAR): Assessment of cardiac and respiratory heart motion in ventricular tachycardia patients - A STOPSTORM.eu consortium review. *Radiother Oncol.* 2023;188:109844.
- [37] Guckenberger M, Andratschke N, Dieckmann K, et al. ESTRO ACROP consensus guideline on implementation and practice of stereotactic body radiotherapy for peripherally located early stage non-small cell lung cancer. *Radiother Oncol.* 2017;124(1):11-17.
- [38] Kiani S, Kutob L, Schneider F, et al. Histopathologic and Ultrastructural Findings in Human Myocardium After Stereotactic Body Radiation Therapy for Recalcitrant Ventricular Tachycardia. *Circ Arrhythm Electrophysiol.* 2020;13:e008753.
- [39] Miszczyk M, Sajdok M, Nożyński J, et al. Histopathological Examination of an Explanted Heart in a Long-Term Responder to Cardiac Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy (STereotactic Arrhythmia Radioablation). *Front Cardiovasc Med.* 2022;9:1742.
- [40] Kaplan LP, Placidi L, Bäck A, et al. Plan quality assessment in clinical practice: Results of the 2020 ESTRO survey on plan complexity and robustness. *Radiother Oncol.* 2022;173:254-261.
- [41] Blanck O, Ipsen S, Chan MK, et al. Treatment Planning Considerations for Robotic Guided Cardiac Radiosurgery for Atrial Fibrillation. *Cureus.* 2016;8(7):e705.
- [42] Gerhard SG, Palma DA, Arifin AJ, et al. Organ at Risk Dose Constraints in SABR: A Systematic Review of Active Clinical Trials. *Pract Radiat Oncol.* 2021;11(4):e355-e365.
- [43] Haskova J, Jedlickova K, Cvek J, et al. Oesophagopericardial fistula as a late complication of stereotactic radiotherapy for recurrent ventricular tachycardia. *Europace.* 2022;24(6):969.
- [44] Blanck O, Buergy D, Vens M, et al. Radiosurgery for ventricular tachycardia: preclinical and clinical evidence and study design for a German multi-center multiplatform feasibility trial (RAVENTA). *Clin Res Cardiol.* 2020;109(11):1319-32.
- [45] Stam B, Peulen H, Guckenberger M, et al. Dose to heart substructures is associated with non-cancer death after SBRT in stage I-II NSCLC patients. *Radiother Oncol.* 2017;123(3):370-375.
- [46] Timmerman R. A Story of Hypofractionation and the Table on the Wall. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys.* 2022;112(1):4-21.

Supplement E3: Rating Score

RATING score sheet		Points	Applicable/ relevant	Answer yes
Questions for the Introduction				
<i>The study aim formulated by research questions</i>				
1	Does the study have a concise and precise study aim, defined with a restricted number of interconnected questions?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>The motivation for the research questions</i>				
2	Has relevant up to date literature been included to support the need for the current study?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3	Does the study address an existing knowledge gap?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Questions for Materials and Methods				
4	Is the global study design adequate for answering the posed research questions?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
5	Is the global study design described in sufficient detail for others to interpret and reproduce the results?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Patient cohort</i>				
6	Are the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the patient cohort described?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
7	Is the clinical patient information of the cohort presented, including disease type, site(s) and clinical staging?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
8	Is the included number of patients stated, explained and justified?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
9	Has there been consideration of the need for ethical and/or legal approval for the study and if needed, is there a statement about this?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Imaging procedures</i>				
10	Have the scanning parameters been reported in sufficient detail (image modalities, equipment model, slice thickness, voxel size, patient position (e.g. head first, supine, etc.) etc.)?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
11	Has the applied immobilisation equipment been described, (e.g. vendor and type, standard settings, etc.) where relevant?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Treatment machine and settings

12	Have the treatment machine and relevant parameters been described with sufficient detail (model, beam energy, MLC, etc.)?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
13	Have the monitor unit reference conditions been defined, where relevant?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Definition of targets and OARs

14	Has GTV definition been described in sufficient detail, with references if possible?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
15	Has CTV definition been described in sufficient detail, with references if possible?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
16	Has the establishment of PTVs (or alternatively robustness settings) been described in sufficient detail?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
17	Have PTV sizes in the patient cohort been described?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
18	Have OAR definitions been described in sufficient detail, with references if possible?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
19	Have PRV margins been described in sufficient detail, with references if available?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Treatment planning system and dose calculation

20	Have all applied dose calculation algorithms been described in sufficient detail?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
21	For any commercial software used, have the manufacturer, algorithms and specific versions been stated?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
22	Have all relevant user parameters and settings in the TPS been reported, e.g. beams, dose grid, control point spacing?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
23	Have all volumes been evaluated with the same software/methodology?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Planning aims and optimisation

24	Are clear planning aims defined, including imposed hard constraints and planning objectives (with or without soft constraints)?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
25	Has the ranking of planning objectives (priorities) been described?	5		<input type="checkbox"/>
26	Is the dose prescription clearly defined?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

- | | | | | |
|----|--|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 27 | Is there a narrative description of the applied optimisation process, including the handling of all objectives with their ranking? | 5 | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 28 | If manual intervention during or after optimisation is allowed, has this been described? | 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Bias mitigation

- | | | | | |
|----|--|----|--|-------------------------------------|
| 29 | Have enough study details been provided such that bias issues could be noted? | 5 | | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| 30 | Has bias been sufficiently mitigated to reliably answer the posed research question? | 10 | | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |

Plan acceptability – minor and major protocol deviations

- | | | | | |
|----|---|---|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 31 | Was the procedure for assessment of plan acceptability well-described? | 1 | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| 32 | Was the procedure for assessment of minor and major protocol deviations well described? | 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Plan (re-)normalisation for plan comparisons

- | | | | | |
|----|--|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 33 | Has plan (re-)normalisation been described sufficiently? | 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
|----|--|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|

Dose-volume parameters for plan evaluation and comparison

- | | | | | |
|----|--|---|--|-------------------------------------|
| 34 | Have sufficiently comprehensive dose-volume parameters been used for plan evaluations and comparisons? | 5 | | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
|----|--|---|--|-------------------------------------|

Population-mean DVHs

- | | | | | |
|----|---|---|-------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| 35 | Has the algorithm for creating population-mean/median DVHs been reported? | 1 | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| 36 | Have the definitions of confidence intervals been included? | 1 | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Plan evaluations by clinicians

- | | | | | |
|----|---|---|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 37 | Have clinicians scored plans to assess quality? | 1 | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 38 | Were plan comparisons by clinicians blinded? | 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Predicted tumour control probability and normal tissue complication probabilities for plan evaluation and comparison

- | | | | | |
|----|---|---|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 39 | Have any applied TCP models been described and referenced? | 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 40 | Have any applied NTCP models been described and referenced? | 1 | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Plan deliverability and complexity

41	Have methods used to assess plan deliverability and complexity been described in sufficient detail?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Composite plan quality metrics</i>				
42	Is there a sufficient basis (e.g. in the literature) for any selected composite plan quality metrics?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
43	Is there an adequate description of the calculation of the composite plan quality metrics?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Planning and delivery times</i>				
44	Has measurement of planning times been described in sufficient detail?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
45	Has the establishment of delivery times been described in sufficient detail?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Statistical analysis</i>				
46	Have proper statistical methods been used and described in sufficient detail?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
47	In case of multiple testing for research questions, has this been handled appropriately?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Questions for Results				
48	Does the provided data contribute to (at least partly) answering all aspects of the research questions, e.g. plan acceptability, dosimetric quality, deliverability and planning and delivery times?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Dose distribution reporting</i>				
49	Are complete summaries of the dose distributions in the patient cohort provided (low doses, high doses, OARs, PTV, patient, etc.)?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
50	Are tables and figures optimised to clearly present the results obtained?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
51	Have the answers to the research questions been illustrated for an example patient by providing dose distributions, DVHs, etc.?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Plan acceptability reporting – minor and major protocol deviations</i>				
52	In case of treatment technique or planning technique comparisons, was plan acceptability reported separately for each technique?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

53	Has plan acceptability been reported in sufficient detail: how many plans were acceptable, how many were not and for what reasons (e.g. violation of hard constraints, violation of soft constraints, other reasons)?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
54	Was there adequate reporting of minor and major protocol deviations?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Deliverability and complexity reporting</i>				
55	Has the deliverability of the plans been adequately reported?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
56	Have plan deliverability and complexity been investigated in sufficient detail in relation to the posed research questions?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Planning and delivery times reporting</i>				
57	Have planning and delivery times been adequately evaluated and reported?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Patient-specific analyses reporting</i>				
58	Is there sufficient description of inter-patient variations in the results presented?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
59	Have outlier patients been reported and has any exclusion from population analyses been sufficiently motivated and explained?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Statistical reporting</i>				
60	Are the p-values reported appropriately?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
61	Are there confidence intervals for the appropriate parameters?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Questions for discussions				
62	Is there an overall interpretation of the data presented in the Results section as to how the posed research questions are answered?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Comparison with literature</i>				
63	Has the study been sufficiently discussed in the context of existing literature?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
<i>Clinical and statistical significance</i>				
64	Does the discussion focus on statistically significant results?	1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
65	Is the potential clinical significance of the results clearly discussed (assuming practical application would be feasible)?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Clinical applicability of the study

66	Is future the clinical applicability sufficiently discussed?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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Study limitations

67	Has the impact of the study limitations on the provided answers to the research questions been sufficiently discussed?	10		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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Future work

68	Has the potential future work arising from the study been discussed?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
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Questions for conclusions

69	Do the presented conclusions represent answers to the posed research questions?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
70	Are the conclusions fully supported by the results?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
71	Are the conclusions a fair summary of all results?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Questions for supplementary

Supplementary materials

72	Is the information presented in the supplementary material of sufficient relevance?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
73	Is the presentation of the included information of sufficient quality, including readability?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
74	Has sufficient underlying data been made available or a willingness to share data been indicated, within local data sharing restrictions?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

RATING remarks

75	Is the RATING score added to the manuscript?	5		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
76	Is the accompanying question table added to the cover letter or the supplementary material?	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

RATING score
RATING fraction

90%

179 of 200